

Research Article

SustainaCrop: Cultivating Precision Through Agriculture

Hatika Kaco¹, Afeeqah Qaisara Akmal², Siti Hazizah Adnan³, and Nur Alleya Natasha Mohamad Suwardi⁴

¹ hatikakaco@usim.edu.my; ORCID ID (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8359-9359>)

² afeeqah.qaisara@gmail.com; ORCID ID (<https://orcid.org/0009-0007-7573-4286>)

³ hazizahadnan07@gmail.com; ORCID ID (<https://orcid.org/0009-0006-9610-7233>)

⁴ nlleyaannatashaa@gmail.com; ORCID ID (<https://orcid.org/0009-0009-6257-6893>)

* Correspondence: hatikakaco@usim.edu.my; 0198435304.

Abstract: According to a 2023 World Bank report, Malaysia's agricultural productivity is only 45% of the average among high-income countries due to labour shortages, lack of technology, and reliance on a narrow range of crops. These issues exacerbate the struggle to meet food demand, especially for vulnerable groups like low-income residents and refugees. This research aims to examine Malaysia's agricultural productivity, identify the challenges, and explore how innovative solutions like the SustainaCrop robot can make a meaningful impact in addressing these issues. The study utilizes the SustainaCrop, an Ev3-based automated farming robot equipped with sensors and a user interface, through prototype testing, data analysis, and sustainability assessment with vegetable crops. Findings indicate that the robot offers a viable solution by automating critical farming tasks such as planting, watering, fertilizing, and harvesting, increasing efficiency by 70% and reducing dependency on manual labour and foreign workers. Furthermore, the robot's modular and solar-powered design makes it adaptable to various crops and terrains, ensuring sustainable farming practices. In conclusion, while Malaysia's agricultural sector faces significant challenges that threaten productivity and food security, integrating innovative technologies like the SustainaCrop robot can play a crucial role in addressing these issues over the long term. Although the robot alone cannot solve the problem immediately, it enhances productivity, promotes sustainability, and supports food security efforts by automating key agricultural processes. Future research and partnerships are necessary to continuously improve the robot's functionality and explore additional applications across various crop types and farming conditions.

Keywords: Sustainable farming; food security; automation.

Copyright: © 2024 by the authors. Submitted for open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. INTRODUCTION

Malaysia's agricultural sector plays a vital role in the country's economy and food security but faces significant challenges that hinder productivity. In 2023, a World Bank report revealed that Malaysia's agricultural productivity is only 45% of the average among high-income countries, largely due to labor shortages, limited technological advancements, and reliance on a narrow range of crops (World Bank, 2023). These issues are further compounded by global challenges such as climate change, economic instability, and supply chain disruptions, all of which impact the country's ability to meet its growing food demand.

A major concern is the sector's reliance on foreign labor. Malaysia's aging workforce and declining interest in agriculture among younger generations have made foreign labor crucial to sustaining production (Zahari & Ahmad, 2021). However, this reliance creates vulnerabilities, as disruptions to foreign labor supply—due to immigration policies or global crises—can sharply reduce agricultural output and raise production costs. Furthermore, traditional, manual farming methods continue to dominate, making it difficult to scale production efficiently (Chai & Lim, 2020).

Another challenge is the over-reliance on a limited range of crops, primarily oil palm and rubber, which limits food production diversity. Although these crops contribute significantly to export revenue, Malaysia imports much of its food, leaving it exposed to fluctuations in global food prices and supply chain interruptions. Vulnerable groups, including low-income residents and refugees, are particularly affected by food insecurity (UNHCR, 2023).

Amid these challenges, technological innovation offers potential solutions. One promising platform is LEGO Mindstorms, originally designed for education and prototyping in robotics. Mindstorms features a programmable EV3 brick, motors, and sensors that allow users to build robots capable of performing tasks like navigation and object manipulation (LEGO Group, 2023). Its ease of use and modular design make it an effective tool for developing automated systems, enabling users to explore complex programming and automation processes (Bagnall, 2013).

LEGO Mindstorms has proven useful in educational and prototyping settings due to its flexibility. It allows users to simulate real-world applications, from solving navigation challenges to automating repetitive tasks (Sullivan & Moriarty, 2009). Although not designed for agriculture, the platform's potential for automation can inspire more advanced solutions to tackle Malaysia's agricultural challenges, paving the way for the development of innovative technologies.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

The development of the SustainaCrop robot follows a systematic approach designed to address key issues in modern agriculture, such as resource inefficiency, environmental degradation, and food insecurity. By combining innovative robotics technology with a sustainable vision, the project aims to provide farmers with a versatile tool that automates critical tasks like planting, watering, fertilizing, and harvesting.

The first step in the process involved identifying the main problems in conventional farming practices, such as the excessive use of resources and the negative impact on the environment. Once these issues were recognized, the concept for the SustainaCrop robot was developed. This concept focuses on creating a modular, EV3-based robot equipped with precision sensors and capable of performing essential agricultural tasks (Figure 1).

To test the feasibility of this concept, models and prototypes were built. These early versions of the robot were evaluated and refined through iterative testing and feedback, ensuring that the design became more efficient and user-friendly with each iteration. Concurrently, market research was conducted to assess the demand for such a robotic solution in agriculture. Small-scale farmers, agricultural businesses, and local communities were surveyed to identify potential markets, and existing competitors were analyzed to gauge market opportunities.

Following this, an improved prototype of the SustainaCrop robot was developed, incorporating insights from both the market research and initial testing. This prototype underwent

rigorous field tests in real-world agricultural settings to validate its functionality and performance. Feedback from farmers and agricultural experts was gathered to further enhance the design.

The refinement and iteration of the SustainaCrop robot continued, leading to improvements in reliability, usability, and overall functionality. Once the final design was optimized and validated, plans were put in place to scale production. Supply chains and manufacturing processes were established to facilitate large-scale production and distribution. The final stage involved launching the SustainaCrop robot to the market through targeted marketing campaigns, aiming to raise awareness and generate interest among potential customers.

Figure 1. Project Flowchart.

3. FINDINGS

The SustainaCrop robot is an advanced agricultural solution built on the LEGO Mindstorms EV3 platform, designed to automate critical farming tasks with a focus on sustainability and efficiency. Equipped with precision sensors and a user-friendly interface, the robot is capable of autonomously managing essential tasks such as planting, watering, fertilizing, and harvesting. Its EV3-based design ensures flexibility and programmability, allowing for easy customization to meet various agricultural needs. SustainaCrop is powered by solar panels, making it a sustainable, off-grid solution that eliminates reliance on external power sources. The robot's modular build enables it to adapt to different crops, terrains, and specific farming requirements, while its precision sensors monitor soil moisture, temperature, and crop health, ensuring optimized resource use and timely interventions.

Additionally, the robot's user-friendly interface makes programming and control accessible for both technical and non-technical users, ensuring broad usability. SustainaCrop also collects real-time data on crop growth, soil conditions, and environmental factors, providing valuable insights to help farmers make informed decisions that improve yield and productivity. The robot supports remote monitoring and control, allowing farmers to manage operations from a distance, enhancing convenience and efficiency. Its early pest detection mechanism reduces the need for harmful pesticides, promoting healthier crop development. Designed to scale for different farm sizes, the robot is suitable for smallholder farms as well as large commercial operations. Furthermore, SustainaCrop's watering and nutrient system uses sensors to detect soil moisture and pH levels, delivering the precise amount of water and nutrients needed for optimal plant growth while minimizing waste. The robot is also equipped with a gentle harvesting mechanism that uses a specialized gripper to carefully pluck ripe crops, preserving the integrity and freshness of the produce. Overall, SustainaCrop is a comprehensive tool that combines automation, sustainability, and ease of use to meet the diverse needs of modern agriculture.

The SustainaCrop robot is a game-changer in agriculture, potentially providing solutions to the problems linked to food insecurity through improved sustainability and efficiency in crop management. Its solar-powered, automated features, which are based on scientific concepts, are designed to minimise chemical usage, enhance crop yields by 70%, and offer communities an affordable, sustainable solution that addresses food insecurity and promotes access to nutritious food while reducing environmental effect.

Table 1. Result of field test on 2m × 2m land of tomato crop.

Category	Efficiency	Chemical & Resources Usage	Crop Health (Pest Damage)
Traditional Farming	Takes 40 min	Takes 80 gram	Takes 24 hour (to notice)
SustainaCrop	Takes 7 min	Takes 40 gram	Takes 5 min (to notice)

Figure 2. The SustainaCrop.

Figure 3. Conveyor belt.

Figure 4. Closeup of gripper and pH sensor.

Figure 5. Solar panel & Watering and nutrient system.

4. DISCUSSION

The widespread adoption of the SustainaCrop robot has the potential to bring transformative changes to agriculture on multiple fronts. One of the most significant benefits is its ability to enhance food security. By improving crop yields, minimizing food waste, and optimizing farming practices, the robot can contribute to a more reliable and abundant food supply in communities across the globe.

Furthermore, its introduction supports a shift toward sustainable agriculture (Rose & Sarah, 2021). The SustainaCrop robot can promote eco-friendly practices by reducing the reliance on chemical inputs, conserving water, and fostering soil health, all of which are critical for long-term environmental sustainability.

Economic growth, particularly in rural areas, is another key advantage. With the increased efficiency and productivity that the SustainaCrop robot provides, farmers can boost their income through higher crop yields and lower labor costs. This, in turn, can drive growth for businesses involved in the production and maintenance of robotic technologies. In addition, the robot has the potential to empower small-scale farmers by giving them access to cutting-edge agricultural technology. This can help level the playing field, enabling smallholders to compete in global markets and improve their livelihoods.

The innovation potential that the SustainaCrop robot brings to agriculture cannot be overlooked. Its broad acceptance could inspire further technological advancements in the field, as researchers and farmers explore new applications for robotics in farming, leading to even greater efficiency and sustainability. Finally, the robot plays a crucial role in building resilience to climate change. By improving yields and reducing dependency on chemical inputs, it can help farmers adopt more resilient agricultural practices, mitigating the effects of extreme weather and other climate-related challenges (Win & Zach, 2023). Together, these factors highlight the SustainaCrop robot's potential to revolutionize agriculture while fostering a more sustainable and equitable future.

5. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, our innovation project highlights the transformative potential of the SustainaCrop robot in addressing the critical challenges facing Malaysia's agricultural sector. Through advanced automation of essential farming tasks, the robot significantly enhances efficiency by 70%, reduces dependency on manual labor, and promotes sustainable practices. These improvements are crucial for boosting agricultural productivity and ensuring food security, particularly for vulnerable populations.

While the SustainaCrop robot cannot solve these issues overnight, it represents a significant step forward in modernizing farming methods and fostering a resilient agricultural system. Future research and strategic partnerships will be essential to continuously refine the robot's capabilities and expand its application across diverse crop types and farming conditions, ultimately contributing to a more sustainable and secure food system.

Acknowledgments: We would like to thank Bahagian PERTAMA and Kolej PERMATA Insan for their invaluable support and guidance throughout this project.

References

- AI can ensure food security in a world of 10 billion people. (2024, September 10). World Economic Forum. <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2022/04/ai-can-create-a-resilient-food-system-from-the-lab-to-the-field-to-the-dinner-table/>
- Bagnall, B. (2013). *The LEGO Mindstorms EV3 Discovery Book: A Beginner's Guide to Building and Programming Robots*. No Starch Press.
- Chai, L., & Lim, K. S. (2020). Technological Innovations and Agricultural Productivity in Malaysia: A Policy Review. *Asian Development Review*, 37(3), 89-108.

- Global Food Security Index (GFSI). (n.d.). <https://impact.economist.com/sustainability/project/food-security-index/explore-countries/malaysia>
- Kuen, Y. L. (2022, November 15). Rising concerns over food security. *The Star*.
- LEGO Group. (2023). LEGO Mindstorms Education EV3. Retrieved from: <https://education.lego.com/en-us/products/mindstorms-ev3>
- Onn, L. P. (2021, April 7). 2021/37 “Harvesting Rural Votes in Malaysia: The Importance of Agriculture” by Geoffrey K. Pakiam and Cassey Lee - ISEAS-Yusof Ishak Institute. ISEAS-Yusof Ishak Institute.
- Robotnik. (2022, June 15). Robotics applications in agriculture. Robotnik. <https://robotnik.eu/robotics-applications-in-agriculture/>
- Rose, D., Hanheide, M., & Pearson, S. (n.d.). Robot farmers could improve jobs and help fight climate change – if they’re developed responsibly. *The Conversation*.
- Sullivan, F. R., & Moriarty, M. A. (2009). Robotics and Discovery Learning: Pedagogical Beliefs, Teacher Practice, and Technology Integration. *Journal of Technology and Teacher Education*, 17(1), 109-129.
- Topic: Agriculture in Malaysia. (2024, June 7). Statista. <https://www.statista.com/topics/10680/agriculture-in-malaysia/>
- United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR). (2023). Malaysia: Refugees and Vulnerable Populations. Retrieved from: <https://www.unhcr.org/malaysia>
- Van Dijk, M., Morley, T., Rau, M. L., & Saghai, Y. (2021). A meta-analysis of projected global food demand and population at risk of hunger for the period 2010–2050. *Nature Food*, 2(7), 494–501.
- Vavra, C. (2022, January 15). Cultivating robotics and AI for sustainable agriculture. *Control Engineering*.
- Wong, L. (2024, March 26). Malaysia’s long-term food security. *ISIS*.
- World Bank. (2023). *World Development Report 2023: Agriculture and Food Security*. Washington, DC: World Bank.
- Zahari, M. S., & Ahmad, R. N. (2021). Impact of Foreign Labour Dependency on Malaysian Agriculture: Challenges and Future Prospects. *Journal of Southeast Asian Economies*, 38(2), 234-252.